

Personalizing long-term health risk assessment of breast cancer radiotherapy: PASSOS risk models

Abstract

In breast cancer radiotherapy, substantial exposure of organs other than the treated breast cannot be entirely avoided, potentially inducing secondary cancer or cardiovascular disease. However, contemporary treatment planning allows for considerable flexibility in the distribution of dose to organs at risk while maintaining the necessary coverage in the target volume. Here, we present an approach to estimate comprehensively the corresponding long-term health risks to support treatment plan optimization.

A central premise of our approach is that cancer induction is a local process. Organ cancer risks are estimated by integrating the organ dose-response relationship over the organ dose distribution. Most organs are exposed to low to moderate doses, such that established and elaborated dose-response models from radiation protection can be applied. However, the highly exposed organs dominate risk. For this reason, we join the low-dose models with specific high-dose models for the lung, contralateral breast, and bone marrow. The high-dose models base upon studies on medical exposure. This approach leads to a combined, in general non-linear dose response, which is supported by data over the whole relevant dose range. For cardiovascular diseases, a linear model is provided, consistent with low- and high-dose studies. The resulting model estimates are widely consistent to rate ratios observed in randomized breast cancer radiotherapy trials. A software tool is supplied to apply the risk models for individual breast cancer patients.

Introduction

Breast cancer is the most frequent cancer in women (Bray et al. 2018). Radiotherapy (RT) reduces the risk of recurrence and improves survival (Early Breast Cancer Trialists' Collaborative et al. 2011). However, due to the general good prognosis especially for loco-regional breast cancer, it is important to pay attention also to the long-term consequences of treatment. Knowledge on these side-effects is important: First, they can be reduced with patient follow-up and prevention measures. Second, there is considerable variation in applying RT with regards to different techniques (3DCRT, IMRT, VMAT; DIBH; prone/supine), and definition of the target volume (partial breast, whole breast, inclusion of lymph nodes). Even within a given setup, some organs at risk may be spared at the cost of some other. However, there is no universally valid optimal RT approach. Optimization of RT treatment and follow-up measures is best performed on an individual basis.

The German project PASSOS (<https://passos.helmholtz-muenchen.de/en>) aimed at providing personalized information on the long-term health risks of breast cancer radiotherapy. This included several aspects: First, organ doses were studied depending on details of the radiation treatment such as the target volume or the irradiation technique but also on the patient's anatomy. Second, risk models were developed to estimate excess radiation risks from dose distributions in almost all organs. Third, lifetime risks were calculated depending on age and tumor prognosis. To make the resulting personalized risk estimates accessible for use in the clinics, the methods were put into a software tool (PASSOS Software). Here, we present the risk models that emerged during the course of the project and which are implemented in the PASSOS software. The

software package will be described and its applications discussed elsewhere. It was developed to estimate risks for patients in Germany but the reported methods are applicable to other populations, too.

Continuous improvement in irradiation facilities has led to substantial changes in the dose distribution during the last decades, aiming for better target volume coverage, avoidance of peak doses, and also minimization of mean doses in organs at risk. This steady evolution impedes a direct evaluation of side effects of contemporary techniques from historical studies. Therefore, risks are estimated based on organ dose distributions and dose-response relationships derived from studies of various radiation exposures. Cancer risk models in the low- and moderate dose region were mainly based on the results from the atomic bomb survivors in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. It is the only cohort that allows to derive organ-specific dose response relationships at low and moderate doses. Furthermore, atomic bomb exposure was acute, similar to radiotherapy applications. With a few exceptions, the risk models were adopted from the ProZES project. ProZES assesses the probability of cancer occurrence from preceding radiation exposure (Ulanowski et al. 2020). For the most frequent cancer sites, such as breast, lung, stomach, colon and thyroid, dedicated cancer risk models were developed. Additional models were developed for groups of functionally related cancer sites. The principle of multi-model inference was used to assess uncertainties from the choice of model. Further methodologic aspects included a stochastic distribution of latency time and risk transfer from a Japanese to a current German population. Several of these issues are also shortly explained below. The methodology and risk models were discussed with external national and international experts and approved by the German Commission on Radiological Protection (SSK) and the Federal Office for Radiation Protection (BfS).

Efforts were undertaken to derive suited models for the most relevant secondary cancer sites in breast cancer RT, the lung, contralateral breast and leukaemia. These organs can receive high doses, and a literature search was thus performed on studies of risk after medical exposure. A central premise adopted in this manuscript is that neither the models derived for high doses may be extrapolated to low doses nor the other way round. An approximate model over the full dose range may be established by joining dose responses from low- and high dose models. Organ cancer risks are approximately calculated by integrating the joined dose response over the organ dose-volume histogram. Low-dose models thus gain in relative importance with improvements in sparing organs at risk. Finally, efforts were also undertaken to derive a model on cardiovascular diseases. No indications were found for a non-linear dose response in the relevant dose range, such that no separation into low- and high-dose models was necessary. Models for all endpoints include an elaborate consideration of uncertainties and a model for the latency of risk.

Methods

Main late health risks of breast cancer radiotherapy are cardiac complications and secondary cancer. In the following, we will focus on the approach of cancer risk modeling. Specifics of cardiac risk estimation are described in the specific subsection.

General approach of cancer risk modeling

Integration of the dose-response relationship

An important property of radiotherapy dose distributions is the strong dose gradient at the field border. It can lead to an order of magnitude decline in dose or even more even in a single organ,

and can lead to very different organ doses depending on individual anatomy. To deal with this situation, we assume that radiation-induced organ cancer risk can be calculated by summing up the cancer risk in each voxel within the organ.

$$ERR = \frac{1}{V} \int ERR(d(x))dV \quad (1)$$

Here, $ERR(d)$ is the dose-response relationship, or more precisely, the excess relative risk for dose d . The volume integral is confined to the volume V of some organ, and $d(x)$ denotes the local dose at some position within the organ. This way, an excess relative risk (ERR) can be calculated for any dose distribution from a dose-response relationship ($ERR(d)$). It should be noted that Eq. (1) is motivated assuming cancer induction to be a local process and the absence of regions of particular radiosensitivity within the organ. If the dose-response relationship follows the Linear-No-Threshold approach, $ERR(d) = ERR_{pd} d$, the integration collapses to yield the mean organ dose, $ERR = ERR_{pd} d_{mean}$.

Low-dose models

Most organs in the body receive only low to moderate doses during breast cancer radiotherapy. For low doses, dose inhomogeneity and fractionation can be expected to be less relevant as cells are typically able to repair most of the radiation damage. Therefore, we apply the cancer risk models previously derived in the ProZES project (Ulanowski et al. 2020). For most organs, ProZES models are based on the atomic bomb survivor data and are thus valid up to moderate doses of a few Gy. Nevertheless, we term these models “low-dose” in the following for simplicity. Organs with infrequent cancers were grouped functionally and for similar dependence of the risk with age and radiation dose. In total, there are 17 risk models in ProZES comprising virtually all cancer sites. General modelling approaches pursued in ProZES are sketched below.

Approach to derive high-dose models

Some organs at risk receive high doses since they are close to or even partially within the treatment field, and risk cannot be described by the models developed in ProZES. Therefore, relevant studies were identified for cancers of the lung and contralateral breast and leukaemia by performing a search on PubMed as well as by reference tracking using recent reviews and articles. Information on each publication was extracted to a spreadsheet, including the age group of exposed individuals, diseases treated with radiotherapy, analyzed endpoint, sample size, length of follow up, and statistical model with type of dose-response analysis.

For lung and breast cancer, a linear risk model was obtained by meta-analysis. For each study that did not report a linear ERR_{pd} estimate but instead provided results for dose categories with associated relative risks, the following methods were used to obtain a linear ERR_{pd} estimate with confidence interval. The reference dose for each given dose category was set to the category mean or median dose if reported. When studies did not report category means or medians, the reference dose was set to the mid-point of the interval (Doi et al. 2014). When the highest dose category had no upper boundary, its reference dose was set to the lower boundary plus the length of the next highest interval (Doi et al. 2014). A linear ERR_{pd} estimate was derived as the slope from an inverse-variance weighted linear regression of the relative risks on the category reference doses without intercept and an offset of 1 (Little 2001). The variance of a category’s relative risk estimate was calculated based on the width of its confidence interval assuming a log-normal distribution. The confidence interval for the pooled ERR_{pd} estimate was calculated using parametric bootstrapping with 1000 replicates assuming a log-normal distribution with the derived category variance (Doi et al. 2014). Finally, the individual ERR_{pd} estimates from different studies were pooled for lung and breast cancer, using a random-effects meta-analysis where the

standard deviations were derived from the ERR_{pd} confidence intervals assuming a log-normal distribution (Viechtbauer 2010).

For leukaemia, the different studies were not pooled, see the section on leukaemia. No attempt was made to estimate radiation induced risks of skin, soft tissue and bone cancer and lymphoma. These endpoints are difficult to model, as data on risks are scarce over the full dose range, organ dose-volume histograms are difficult to determine, and the absolute increase in cancer cases is moderate (Clarke et al. 2005; Taylor et al. 2017). Moreover, no attempt was made to estimate radiation induced risk of secondary cancer in the treated breast, as the authors are not aware of any study on this subject.

Finally, for lung and breast cancer and leukaemia, the derived high-dose models were combined with low-dose models interpolating the dose-response relationship in a transition region between low and high doses. Details are specified in the endpoint specific sections.

Mixed multiplicative and additive risk transfer

In order to include the uncertainty concerning the risk transfer from the Japanese atomic bomb survivor cohort to the present German population, a mixed transfer is employed in ProZES. This means that the excess absolute risk (EAR) estimated for Germany is based on an average of two contributions. The first is derived from the ERR in the atomic bomb survivors, multiplied with German population incidence rates (German Centre for Cancer Registry Data (ZfKD) 2013). The second equals the EAR fitted directly in the atomic bomb survivors. While the first contribution corresponds to the same *relative* radiation risk in the two populations, the second corresponds to the same *absolute* radiation risk.

Smoking intensity is an important risk factor for lung cancer. Therefore, the transfer procedure is applied in this study for defined smoking. The method to estimate smoking dependent lung cancer risk in the German population is described in detail in the Supplementary Material. While a mixed, multiplicative and additive risk transfer was employed for the low-dose models, purely multiplicative risk transfer was chosen for the high dose models, consistent with the assumption of compatible relative risks in the meta-analyses.

Uncertainty evaluation

Uncertainties can be substantial in all steps of risk estimation. Following the ProZES approach, our models therefore yield random samples of possible results instead of a single best estimate. In this study, we report medians and intervals containing 95% of the samples. The following sources of uncertainty were taken into account:

- model selection, by applying several radiation risk models with respective weights when there was ambiguity on the dose-response relationship
- statistical uncertainty, by taking into account confidence intervals and correlations of model parameters and uncertainty in cancer rates at young ages
- uncertainty in risk transfer, by sampling the weight of multiplicative versus additive risk transfer for the low-dose models,
- uncertainty in lag-time, by allowing the lag-time for solid cancers to vary within 3 to 4 years and within 1.25 to 1.75 years for leukaemia.

Lung cancer

High-dose risk model

In the meta-analysis for lung cancer after moderate and high doses, two studies were included on irradiation of patients for Hodgkin lymphoma (Gilbert et al. 2003; Kaldor et al. 1992), one on peptic ulcer (Carr et al. 2002), one on benign breast disease (Mattsson et al. 1997), and two

studies on breast cancer patients (Grantzau et al. 2014; Inskip et al. 1994). A study on patients with tuberculosis (Howe 1995) was excluded as lung disease or the non-radiation treatment potentially could have influenced the risk of lung cancer. Moreover, a study on patients treated with X-rays for ankylosing spondylitis (Weiss et al. 1994) was excluded as patients were compared to the general population to estimate the risk. The result of the meta-analysis is a linear model in dose d

$$ERR(d) = (e^{\beta} - 1) d \quad (2)$$

Here, β is sampled from a normal distribution with mean 0.15 and standard deviation 0.05. The cumbersome parameterization of the linear coefficient was chosen to reflect the structure of the uncertainty derived from the meta-analysis that is based on an exponential model of the relative risk. The unit of dose is Gy. The annual absolute excess risk (EAR) is derived by multiplication of the excess relative risk (ERR) with the personalized, smoking behavior-related and age-dependent baseline risk, see the Supplementary Material.

Low-dose risk and model combination

For the lungs, ProZES refers to the model of (Furukawa et al. 2010) which is based on the atomic bomb survivor data with follow up until 1999. In the meantime an update of the analysis and the data was published (Cahoon et al. 2017) with ten additional years of follow up. Therefore, we employ the updated data for the low dose regime in the lungs. Following the approach of ProZES, only significant parameters were retained in the model. On the other hand, as the radiation dose response depends on smoking intensity in the model, parameters for unknown smoking were introduced in the radiation response modification for both sexes.

The low-dose model is assumed to be valid for the organ fraction that is exposed to less than 0.5 Gy, the high dose model for the organ fraction that is exposed to more than 1 Gy. These values have been chosen as one of the studies (Grantzau et al. 2014) importantly contributing to our meta-analysis strongly indicates that our low-dose model overestimates the risk already in this dose range. Linear interpolation was adapted in between 0.5 Gy and 1 Gy. If the low-dose model evaluated at 0.5 Gy provides a larger risk estimate than the high dose model evaluated at 1 Gy, the geometric mean of these two values was chosen to connect the models horizontally. This procedure guarantees that the interpolation between low-dose and high-dose model does not lead to local minima in the dose-response relationship.

Contralateral breast cancer

High-dose risk

Included in the meta-analysis were three studies on patients with Hodgkin lymphoma (Bhatia et al. 1996; Travis et al. 2003; van Leeuwen et al. 2003), one on leukaemia (Curtis et al. 1992), one on tuberculosis (Boice et al. 1991), two on childhood cancer (Guibout et al. 2005; Inskip et al. 2009), and most suitable for PASSOS, two studies on breast cancer radiotherapy (Storm et al. 1992; Stovall et al. 2008). Studies on patients irradiated at infancy were not included as the breast undergoes substantial alterations in youth. Furthermore, also a study on radiation treatment of benign breast disease (Mattsson et al. 1993) was not taken into account to exclude any potential impact of the treated disease on later cancer risk. The same methods and parametrization, Eq. (2), were applied as for lung cancer. According to results from the meta-analysis the parameter was sampled from a normal distribution with mean 0.17 and standard deviation of 0.07.

Low-dose risk and model combination

The low-dose model was directly adopted from ProZES and is thus based on the pooled analysis of Preston et al (Preston et al. 2002). The pooled analysis is based on data from atomic bomb

survivors and cohorts with medical radiation exposure. Therefore, a larger range of validity was assumed for the low-dose model, and interpolation between low- and high-dose models was performed between 1 Gy and 4 Gy.

Leukaemia

High-dose risk

The bone marrow is distributed over many bones in the body and thus exhibits the strongest dose gradient in breast-cancer radiotherapy. There is evidence in the literature that the shape of the dose-response relationship is non-linear (Blettner and Boice 1991; Curtis et al. 1994). However, only some studies on high doses have tested non-linearities and there is no generally accepted functional form of the dose-response relationship. Therefore, a meta-analysis is not feasible and we include results of four different studies directly and sample the results from each study with a probability of 25%. Here we do not include studies on leukaemia after childhood cancer and put emphasis on studies which evaluated the existence of non-linearities in the dose-response.

The first model applied was recommended in (Blettner and Boice 1991):

$$1 + ERR(d) = [1 + 0.1(e^{\beta_1} - 1) d] \exp(-0.1(e^{\beta_2} - 1) d) \quad (3)$$

Here, d refers to the local dose in a subvolume of the bone marrow. When integrating the dose-response relationship $ERR(d)$ over the bone marrow containing parts of the skeleton, Eq. (1), integration must be weighted by the relative bone marrow content (Simonetto et al. 2019b). As before, the cumbersome parametrization of the coefficients was chosen to properly reflect the uncertainty structure. The parameters β_1 and β_2 were sampled from a multivariate normal distribution with means 2.28 and 0.58, standard deviations of 0.6 and 0.25 and a correlation of 0.7 as read off from Fig. 2 in (Blettner and Boice 1991).

In reference (Curtis et al. 1994) both, linear and non-linear models are presented with a preference for a non-linear model only in the case of brachytherapy. Therefore, we include both a linear model and the best non-linear model, each with a weight of 12.5%. For the linear model, again parameterization Eq. (2) is applied sampling β from a normal distribution with mean 0.12 and standard deviation 0.05. The non-linear model is analogous to the one used in (Blettner and Boice 1991),

$$1 + ERR = [1 + (e^{\beta_1} - 1) d_{mean}] \exp(-\beta_2 d_{mean})$$

with the important difference, however, that the mean dose is applied and thus no integration over the organ volume, Eq. (1), needs to be performed. To approximate the published best estimate and confidence intervals, the parameter β_1 is sampled from a normal distribution with mean 1.74 and standard deviation 0.49 and β_2 from a normal distribution with mean 0.9 and standard deviation 0.27.

In (Weiss et al. 1995) non-linear models depending on time since exposure tse are clearly preferred. We adopt the best model according to the Akaike Information Criterion.

$$ERR(d) = (e^{\beta_1} - 1) d (\beta_2)^d e^{-0.058(tse-10)}$$

Parameter uncertainty for the dependence on time since exposure is not presented in (Weiss et al. 1995) but is likely to be small given the strong impact of time since exposure on the goodness-of-fit. The parameter β_1 was sampled from a normal distribution with mean 2.59 and standard deviation 0.71. The parameter β_2 was sampled from a normal distribution with mean 0.53 and standard deviation of 0.16. Uncertainties were chosen to reproduce 95% confidence intervals in table VIII of (Weiss et al. 1995). Beyond the 95% level, however, sampled values for β_2 , were confined in (0.01, 0.99) in order not to obtain sporadic samples with a huge, exponentially increased risk.

The last model included is the linear model based on (Travis et al. 2000),

$$ERR(d) = 0.1 (e^{\beta} - 1) d$$

with β sampled from a normal distribution with mean 1.31 and standard deviation 2.76.

Low-dose risk and model combination

For low doses, ProZES models are adopted which were derived based on data on the atomic bomb survivors. These models are sensitive to the specific type of leukaemia, are non-linear in dose, and take into account dependencies in age and age at exposure. Two slight modifications were applied compared to the model evaluation in ProZES. First, dose-responses with risks below the linear model are excluded in ProZES in order to be conservative. In PASSOS the aim is not a conservative but a realistic estimate. Therefore, no distinction was made between linear- and non-linear models. Second, for chronic lymphocytic leukaemia, only the male but not the female specific risk model yielded a radiation risk. Therefore, we apply a mixture of the gender independent and the female specific model.

Given the many models involved and the strong non-linearities, another approach was adopted to combine low- and high-dose models for leukaemia than was used for the lung and contralateral breast. The dose-volume histogram was split into a low-dose and a high-dose regime. Low-dose models were applied to the low-dose regime, high-dose models to the high-dose regime, and the results were added. The split point was sampled uniformly in the interval from 0 to 1 Gy. This low split point was chosen due to the strong sensitivity of potentially leukemic cells with regard e.g. to cell killing (Weiss et al. 1995).

Cardiovascular Diseases

For cardiovascular diseases, mortality was estimated instead of incidence. Reasons included the wide range of different severities for incidence of cardiovascular disease, and the absence of a national register of cardiovascular incidence. Therefore, national death statistics were used (Federal Health Reporting 2014). As breast cancer irradiation affects mainly the chest, only diseases with heart involvement were included (ICD-10 codes: I05-I52). No separate models for low- and high dose were derived as there is no obvious way to combine them: different parts of the heart cannot be assumed to deteriorate independently of each other, contrary to the assumptions underlying Eq. (1). Therefore, the following model was applied to calculate total cardiovascular risk:

$$ERR = (e^{\beta} - 1)d_{mean} \times \begin{cases} \Theta + (1 - \Theta) \frac{tse}{20}, & tse < 20 \\ 1, & tse \geq 20 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The coefficient β was derived from a meta-analysis as described above for cancer high-dose models and uncertainty evaluation proceeded analogously. Despite different doses and endpoints, the different studies included in the meta-analysis (Carr et al. 2005; Cutter et al. 2015; Darby et al. 2013; Green et al. 2001; Guldner et al. 2006; Hancock et al. 1993; Hooning et al. 2007; Little et al. 2012; Mulrooney et al. 2009; Tukenova et al. 2010; van der Pal et al. 2012; van Nimwegen et al. 2016; Zablotska et al. 2014) were quite consistent to a linear dose-response relationship, and β was accordingly sampled from a normal distribution with mean 0.08 and standard deviation 0.01. However, it was not possible to deduce any lag-time between exposure and occurrence of first radiation induced cardiovascular mortality cases. In particular, there is conflicting evidence from two large studies on cardiovascular events after radiotherapy of the breast: While radiation risk sets in immediately after radiotherapy and tends to decrease thereafter in (Darby et al. 2013), a steady increase in risk during the first decades was observed in (Henson et al. 2013). To account for this uncertainty, a linear increase in risk was implemented during the first 20 years, see Eq. (4), and the unknown fraction Θ of the relative risk that sets in without any delay was sampled from a uniform distribution in (0,1).

Results

Dose-response relationships from merging low- and high-dose models and resultant risk estimates

The combination of different models for low- and high-dose regimes implies some non-linearity in the transition region, even if both low- and high-dose risk models are linear. The high dose models are relative risk models insensitive to any dose-effect modifiers. On the other hand, the ProZES models applied for the low dose regime take into account the effect of age at exposure, age, and – for lung cancer - smoking intensity. As a consequence, dose-response relationships from merging low- and high-dose models depend on dose-effect modifiers.

In order to give some guidance on the relevance of specific cancer sites and the dose-effect modifiers for the long-term health risk of breast cancer radiotherapy, risks were evaluated for a dose distribution derived from a standard left-sided whole breast 3D-conformal (3D-CRT) treatment plan for a woman with normal anatomy. For plan details see (Kundrat et al. 2019; Simonetto et al. 2019b).

Lung cancer

In Fig. 1 we show the resulting lung cancer dose-response curve for a 60-year-old woman after radiotherapy at age 50 in dependence on her smoking behavior. The mean lung dose of our exemplary dose distribution is 3.8 Gy. Due to the non-linearity, however, the mean dose is not sufficient to calculate the risk, but the organ cancer risk is obtained from integrating the local risk over the organ volume, Eq. (1). As a consequence, there is a moderate variation of the ERR with smoking intensity for the exemplary dose distribution: from ERR=0.80 for a 60-year old woman who smokes 5 cigarettes per day down to ERR=0.60 for a strong smoker with 25 cigarettes per day. On the other hand, excess absolute risks given per 10^5 person years at age 60 strongly increase with smoking: from 20 for a non-smoker, 68 for a woman who has been smoking 5 cigarettes per day since age 20, to 356 for a woman who has been smoking 25 cigarettes instead. This largely enhanced EAR follows from the strong impact of smoking on the baseline risk.

Fig. 1: Lung cancer dose-response relationship for a 60 year old women irradiated at age 50, evaluated for different smoking intensities. Shaded regions correspond to 95% confidence intervals.

Contralateral breast cancer

For radiation induced contralateral breast cancer, the low-dose risk model includes a strong dependence on the women's age. The resulting dose-response curve of the combined low- and high-dose model can be seen in Fig. 2 for ten years after treatment at age 40 or 70. For our exemplary dose distribution with a mean contralateral breast dose of 1.0 Gy we evaluate an ERR of 0.19 and an EAR of 42 per 10^5 person years for the woman treated at age 40. For a treatment at age 70, we evaluate ERR = 0.06 and EAR = 24 per 10^5 person years.

Fig. 2: Breast cancer dose-response relationship, evaluated for different ages. Shaded regions correspond to 95% confidence intervals.

Leukaemia

There is no generally accepted dose-response relationship for induction of leukaemia and it may well be non-linear. Therefore, we have applied non-linear models not only for the low- but also for the high-dose region. Dose-response relationships of the models considered and the combined model are presented in Fig. 3. As can be seen, the low-dose model is more consistent with the non-linear models and shifts the combined model to relatively higher risks. Dose-response relationships are very different for the different models considered, and even include negative risk. The combined model features a formidable uncertainty as a result of model uncertainty and parameter uncertainties of the models included.

Fig. 3: Dose response curves for leukaemia induction for a 60-year-old women irradiated at age 50. Colored lines correspond to the different dose responses entering the high-dose model. Shown in gray are the low- and high-dose model. The low-dose model contributes only up to 1 Gy. The black line correspond to the combined model, which is identical to the high-dose model above 1 Gy.

To give an impression on the contributions of each model we present in Table 1 the calculated ERRs for our exemplary dose distribution with a mean dose to the red bone marrow of 0.85 Gy and a volume fraction with more than 10 Gy (V10Gy) of 2%. The corresponding dose-volume histogram in the red bone marrow is presented in figure 2 of (Simonetto et al. 2019b). Each of the ERRs in Table 1 were obtained from applying one of the high-dose models to the whole dose range of the exemplary dose distribution. Best estimates of the ERR vary from 0.11 to 1.6 and some of the 95% confidence intervals do not overlap. The combined model includes all of the high-dose models together with the low-dose model as explained in the Methods section. The inclusion of the low-dose model increases the risk estimate. Still, the ERR of the combined model is lower than the average of high-dose model results. The reason is that the best estimate of the combined model follows the median of the uncertainty distribution and not the mean.

(Travis et al. 2000)	(Curtis et al. 1994)	(Curtis et al. 1994)	(Blettner and Boice 1991)	(Weiss et al. 1995)	Combined model
linear	linear	non-linear	non-linear	non-linear	non-linear
0.23 (0.01; 0.94)	0.11 (0.02; 0.21)	1.3 (-0.16; 5.6)	0.22 (0.06; 0.66)	1.6 (0.29; 7.5)	0.48 (0.11; 3.5)

Table 1: ERR and 95% CIs for the different models contributing to the high-dose model and for the combined model, applied to an exemplary dose distribution derived with a standard whole breast 3D-conformal radiotherapy plan, and evaluated for a woman at age 60, irradiated at age 50.

Risk estimates for different sites

For comparison of organ-specific risk estimates, we apply the models to our exemplary dose-distribution of 3D-CRT left-sided breast irradiation. Results are presented here for a fictive non-smoking woman for ten years after treatment at age 50. For illustration, mean organ doses are listed in Table 2, although cancer risks are calculated in general by integration over the organ dose-volume histogram, Eq. (1). We show explicit doses and risks only for several organs in Table 2, selected according to organ dose and frequency of cancer. Among the organs not shown, urinary system cancers are the most relevant for our example with an EAR of altogether 5.8 per 10^5 person years. Finally, the overall values for all solid cancers but breast are higher than the sum of the best risk estimates of individual cancer sites because the underlying probability distributions are not symmetric.

	Mean organ dose [Gy]	ERR	EAR per 10^5 person years
Heart /cardiovascular mortality	3.2	0.19 (0.12; 0.28)	11 (7.1; 17)
Contralateral breast (cancer)	1.0	0.12 (0.05; 0.26)	35 (15; 77)
Lung (cancer), nonsmoker	3.8	0.75 (0.39; 1.2)	20 (10; 32)
Lung (cancer), 25 cigarettes per day	3.8	0.60 (0.24; 1.0)	356 (138; 641)
Oesophagus (cancer)	0.61	0.21 (0.09; 0.56)	1.2 (0.52; 3.2)
Pancreas (cancer)	0.53	0.18 (0.08; 0.49)	4.0 (1.7; 11)
Stomach (cancer)*	0.69	0.32 (0.15;0.53)	5.3 (2.6; 8.9)
Colon (cancer)	0.14	0.05 (0.00; 0.22)	2.1 (0.2; 9.5)
All solid cancer but breast, nonsmoker		0.13 (0.09; 0.18)	51 (34; 73)
Red bone marrow / leukaemia	0.85	0.48 (0.11; 3.5)	7.8 (1.9; 57)
All cancer but breast, nonsmoker		0.15 (0.10; 0.27)	60 (40; 111)

Table 2: Mean organ doses to several organs and calculated excess relative (ERR) and excess absolute risks (EAR) for cardiovascular disease mortality or cancer incidence. Results are shown for a dose distribution of an exemplary 3D-conformal radiotherapy plan. Risk calculations were performed for a woman at age 60, treated with breast cancer radiotherapy at age 50.

*As justified in the Discussion, only multiplicative risk transfer was used for stomach cancer. Much larger risks were obtained for mixed additive and multiplicative risk transfer, ERR = 1.6 (0.33; 3.8) and EAR = 26 (5.4; 63) per 10^5 person years.

Software

The presented risk models were implemented in a software tool that allows to calculate the risk of breast cancer radiotherapy for various dose distributions and patient's age and smoking behavior (PASSOS Software). Further details to the software and examples of clinical applications will be discussed elsewhere.

Discussion

Comparison to randomized trials

In this study, we apply dose-response relationships from studies on radiation risk in various cohorts to estimate the long-term risk of breast cancer radiotherapy. However, excess risk of radiotherapy versus no radiotherapy can also be determined from the follow up of randomized trials. The latter approach has the disadvantage that organ doses were not assessed in general and it is thus difficult to extrapolate the risks from historic trials to contemporary treatments. Nevertheless, a comparison of results may be instructive. Therefore, we show rate ratios of different late health effects for radiotherapy versus no radiotherapy (Taylor et al. 2017) in Table 3. For some organs retrospective dose assessment was performed, and corresponding mean doses are shown together with the rate ratios in Table 3. Rate ratios may be compared to relative risks, or, after subtraction of unity, to the excess relative risks from Table 2. It is advantageous to compare relative risks instead of absolute numbers, as the latter depend strongly on age and generally on the baseline incidence.

	Mean dose [Gy]	Rate ratio (95% CI)
Heart / all cardiac deaths	6.3	1.30 (1.15; 1.46)
Contralateral breast cancer	NA	1.20 (1.08; 1.33)
Lung (cancer)	9.6	2.10 (1.48; 2.98)
Oesophagus (cancer)	8.4	2.42 (1.19; 4.92)
Pancreas cancer	NA	1.64 (0.98; 2.76)
Stomach cancer	NA	0.80 (0.55; 1.17)
Colon cancer	NA	1.15 (0.91; 1.45)
Leukaemia	NA	1.71 (1.05; 2.79)
All cancer but breast	NA	1.23 (1.12; 1.36)

Table 3: Estimated average mean organ doses and rate ratios adopted from an analysis of randomized trials of breast cancer radiotherapy versus no radiotherapy (Taylor et al. 2017).

Comparing mean organ doses between the randomized trials and our results, Table 2, heart and lung doses are about twice as large in the trials, and the dose to the oesophagus is even about tenfold. These higher doses can partially be explained by outdated radiotherapy techniques, and especially the high dose to the oesophagus resulted from inclusion of the internal mammary chain and supraclavicular fossa in many of the randomized trials. Comparing risks, our estimates for cardiac risks, lung and oesophageal cancer are lower compared to the randomized trials, and about consistent with the reduction in the organ doses. Regarding other organs, risks are more difficult to compare, as organ doses are unknown for the randomized trials. For most sites, risks are of similar size and uncertainties are large for both approaches. Only for stomach cancer, results from the meta-analysis disagreed with our estimates. However, the estimation of stomach cancer risk was peculiar. As for most other organs, risk models were adopted from ProZES (Ulanowski et al. 2020) and are based on atomic bomb survivors. Following the procedure in ProZES, risk was transferred to the German population in parts relatively (“multiplicatively”) and in parts absolutely (“additively”). However, the baseline risk of stomach cancer in the model derived from atomic bomb survivors is about tenfold higher compared to the modern German population. Therefore, the transfer of absolute risk numbers yields a high risk also in the target population. If we transfer stomach cancer risk only multiplicatively, i.e. assuming the same relative risks in the atomic bomb survivors and the German population, our estimate for the stomach cancer risk is drastically reduced, by about a factor of 5. The resulting ERR = 0.32 (95%CI: 0.15; 0.54) is much

closer to the risk observed in the trials. The latter, however, is even negative, probably due to statistical fluctuation. For this reason, we have refined the software in using only relative risk transfer for stomach cancer risk.

The dose response relationship and its modifiers

Before discussing our approach in general, some words are in order regarding each endpoint for which a high-dose model was developed. For lung cancer, the atomic bomb survivors are the only data source known to the authors showing high relative radiation risk per dose for non-smokers and little to no risk for heavy smokers. Studies after medical radiation exposure clearly show significant radiation risk for smokers, consistent with a multiplicative radiation-smoking interaction (Ford et al. 2003; Kaufman et al. 2008; Neugut et al. 1994; Travis et al. 2002).

Therefore, no modification of radiation risk with smoking was built into the high-dose model. As a consequence, the combined lung-cancer dose-response relationship is either strongly super- or sublinear at low doses, depending on smoking intensity (Fig. 1). This dose-response is biologically questionable but represents a compromise that reflects the present knowledge. In any case, total radiation induced lung cancer relative risk is not strongly affected by smoking intensity according to our model but absolute risks strongly increase with the number of cigarettes smoked.

Consequently, smoking cessation can be expected to reduce baseline as well as radiation induced absolute risks of lung cancer.

For breast cancer, our low- and high dose models are similar with respect to the relative risks per dose (Fig. 2). In the low-dose model, risk depends on the age at radiation exposure, while we did not include such dependence in the high dose model. Indeed, there is conflicting evidence on this dependence in studies from medical radiation exposure. While a clear decline of radiation risk with higher age at exposure was observed in a survey of different studies (Schneider and Walsh 2015) no such dependence was observed in randomized trials of breast cancer radiotherapy (Taylor et al. 2017).

With regards to the induction of leukaemia, it is generally acknowledged that risk estimates obtained from the atomic bomb survivors can not be applied to higher doses (National Council on Radiation Protection and Measurements 2011). Given the high radiosensitivity of the hematopoietic system, killing or sterilization of potentially leukaemic cells is expected above exposures of about 1 Gy (Weiss et al. 1995) and this dose is exceeded locally even for a single fraction in breast cancer radiotherapy. While non-linearity of the dose-response relationship is thus expected, there is no generally accepted form of the dose-response function and estimates are very imprecise. Therefore, we have included also linear models from studies of leukaemia induction after radiotherapy. However, extrapolation of the linear models may strongly fail as they were derived for radiotherapy applications with mean doses to the red bone marrow of about 10 Gy (Curtis et al. 1994; Travis et al. 2000), well above the mean dose in our example, 0.85 Gy. For cardiovascular diseases, a linear dose-response was adopted from a meta-analysis of high-dose studies with no contribution from low-dose studies. However, this is not a limitation as our best estimate $ERR_{pd} = 0.08$ per Gy is anyway consistent with results from e.g. the atomic bomb survivors, $ERR_{pd} = 0.136 \pm 0.044$ per Gy (Schöllnberger et al. 2018).

General limitations and future aims

Low-dose models derived from the atomic bomb survivors are known to fail at high radiotherapy doses (Berrington de Gonzalez et al. 2013). Cell sterilization is likely to play a role also in organs other than red bone marrow and modelling has been put forward in this direction (Sachs and Brenner 2005; Schneider 2009; Shuryak et al. 2009). Optimally, a radiobiological model should include effects of fractionation and inhomogeneity and explain differences in dose-response relationships for different organs from results of cell experiments and organ architecture. Here, a

pragmatic approach is followed instead, namely fusing together different sources of information into joined dose-response curves. Organ cancer risks were evaluated by integrating over the dose-response relationship, weighted with corresponding volume fractions of the organ dose distribution. Biologically, this approach is motivated for homogeneous organs assuming no relevant mediation of damage or repair mechanisms over distances of many cells. While these assumptions are certainly not fully met, we still believe that for strong dose gradients our approach is favorable compared to applying mean organ doses.

In this study, we aim for a comprehensive long-term health risk models after breast cancer radiotherapy. Dose exposure of most organs is low to moderate such that established and elaborate cancer risk models could adopted from the ProZES project (Ulanowski et al. 2020). For lung, and breast cancer, leukaemia, and cardiac diseases a literature search and dedicated modelling were performed. Still, some long-term risks are not included. First of all, this study only deals with adverse effects of radiotherapy, ignoring the benefit and the risks in the treated breast. Moreover, risks of skin cancer, soft tissue and bone cancer and lymphoma were not included. In the clinical application, patients and physicians are likely to be more interested in time integrated risks such as the risk until age 80 or the expected years of life lost. Such metrics depend on the individual life expectancy. Therefore, only excess risks ten years after exposure are presented in this manuscript. Integrated metrics can, however, be obtained from the software (PASSOS Software).

Many of the risk models used for this study depend on age and several on age at exposure. Only for lung cancer the radiation risk model includes the modification effect of another risk factor, i.e. smoking intensity. As a result, the smoking intensity was also used for computation of the baseline risk. To improve personalization of risk estimates, this approach could be extended to include risk factors in the baseline risk even if they have no effect on the (relative) radiation risk (Simonetto et al. 2019a).

Conclusion

Late health consequences of radiotherapy are often estimated based on models from radiation protection or taking into account only few organs (Joosten et al. 2014). Here, we provide a more appropriate and comprehensive set of models, based on data from low- and high dose models, and taking into account many sources of uncertainty. The models can easily be accessed via the published software.

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